

ISSN 2181-9505
Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9505

Philosophy and Life

FALSAFA VA HAYOT • ФИЛОСОФИЯ И ЖИЗНЬ

2024 № 4 (27)

ISSN 2181-9505
Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9505

Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy Universiteti
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi
Imom Buxoriy xalqaro ilmiy-tadqiqot markazi
O'zbekiston falsafa jamiyati

Национальный Университет Узбекистана имени Мирзо Улугбека
Международный научно-исследовательский центр Имам Бухари
при Кабинете Министров Республики Узбекистан
Философское общество Узбекистана

The National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek
Imam Bukhari International Research Center under the Cabinet of Ministers
of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Philosophical Society of Uzbekistan

**FALSAFA VA HAYOT
XALQARO JURNAL**

**ФИЛОСОФИЯ И ЖИЗНЬ
МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ**

**PHILOSOPHY AND LIFE
INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL**

2024 № 4 (27)

Jurnal bir yilda 4 marta nashr qilinadi.
Журнал выходит 4 раза в год.
The journal is published 4 times in a year.

Toshkent

“Falsafa va hayot” xalqaro jurnal
“Философия и жизнь” международный журнал
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UDK: 81'373.45:82-3(665)+396

 10.5281/zenodo.15805976

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**INVERTED REALITY AND CULTURAL RESPONSE TO MODERNITY
IN WOLE SOYINKA'S THE LION AND THE JEWEL (LE LION ET LA
PERLE)**

Abstract: African dramatic literature is a product of and a response to the society which informs its creativity. Nigerian playwrights such as Wole Soyinka, therefore, have been generating ideas for their dramatic creativity from the trajectory of events that occur at their remote and immediate environments. With the qualitative approach of textual analysis and literature review, the article adopts tenets of postcolonial theory to critique Wole Soyinka's *The Lion and the Jewel* (*Le Lion Et La Perle*) – a play that has been critiqued by some scholars from the perspectives of culture/ideological conflicts. The socio-cultural relevance of the play, perhaps, has informed its translation into French language. For this article, however, the English version of the play is used based on the fact that English has wider coverage in literary discourses. With the theoretical and analytical approach in this article, the play is discussed beyond the spectra of culture and ideological conflicts by considering its characterization and plot. The cultural response to modernity is the advocacy for cultural synthesis of tradition and modernity for sustainable modernity.

Keywords: Soyinka's postcolonial drama, African cultural nationalism, tradition versus modernity

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**ИНВЕРСИОННАЯ РЕАЛЬНОСТЬ И КУЛЬТУРНЫЙ ОТКЛИК НА
МОДЕРННОСТЬ В ПЬЕСЕ «ЛЕВ И ЖЕМЧУЖИНА» ВОЛЕ СОЙИНКИ**

Аннотация. Африканская драматургия является как продуктом, так и ответом на общество, питающее её творческое начало. Таким образом, нигерийские драматурги, такие как Воле Сойинка, черпают вдохновение для

своего драматического творчества из событий, происходящих как в ближайшем, так и в отдалённом окружении. Используя качественный подход текстового анализа и литературного обзора, данная статья опирается на принципы постколониальной теории для анализа пьесы Воле Сойинки *Лев и Жемчужина* — произведения, которое уже было рассмотрено рядом исследователей с точки зрения культурных и идеологических конфликтов. Социокультурная значимость пьесы, вероятно, послужила причиной её перевода на французский язык. Однако в данной статье используется английская версия, так как английский язык шире распространён в литературоведческих дискуссиях. Посредством теоретического и аналитического подхода пьеса рассматривается шире, чем просто как отражение культурных и идеологических противоречий — акцент также делается на характеристике персонажей и развитии сюжета. Культурный отклик на модернизм здесь заключается в стремлении к культурному синтезу традиции и современности ради устойчивого будущего.

Ключевые слова: постколониальная драма Сойинки, африканский культурный национализм, традиция против модерности

Azeez Akinwumi Sesan

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Osogbo-Nigeria.

WOLE SOYINKA'NING “SHER VA MARVARID” (“LE LION ET LA PERLE”) ASARIDA TESKARI HAQIQAT VA ZAMONAVIYLIKKA MADANIY JAVOB

Annotatsiya: Afrika dramatik adabiyoti — bu jamiyat mahsuli bo‘lib, shu jamiyatning o‘zi ushbu ijodga turtki beradi va unga javob bo‘ladi. Shu boisdan, nigeriyalik dramaturglar, xususan, Vole Soyinka, o‘z atrof-muhitidagi yaqin va uzoq voqealardan ilhom olib dramatik asarlar yaratib kelishgan. Mazkur maqolada matn tahlili va adabiyot sharhi kabi sifatli yondashuv asosida postkolonial nazariya tamoyillari asosida Vole Soyinka qalamiga mansub “Sher va Marvarid” (“Le Lion et la Perle”) dramasi tahlil qilinadi. Mazkur asar ayrim tadqiqotchilar tomonidan madaniyat va mafkuraviy qarama-qarshiliklar nuqtai nazaridan baholangan. Asarning ijtimoiy-madaniy ahamiyati uni fransuz tiliga tarjima qilinishiga sabab bo‘lgan bo‘lishi mumkin. Ammo ushbu maqolada inglizcha nusxadan foydalaniladi, chunki ingliz tili adabiy munozaralarda kengroq qamrovga ega. Teoretik va tahliliy yondashuv asosida ushbu dramaga faqat madaniy va mafkuraviy qarama-qarshiliklar nuqtai nazaridan emas, balki obrazlar va syujet tahlili orqali yondashiladi. Zamonaviylikka madaniy javob sifatida an’anaviylik va zamonaviylikni uyg‘unlashtirish zarurligi ilgari suriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Soyinka postkolonial dramasi, Afrika madaniy millatchiligi, an’ana va zamonaviylik qarama-qarshiligi

INTRODUCTION

A retroactive reflection of the past historical and sociological experiences in Nigeria reveals a fundamental gap in our perception of realities and the notional interpretation of the events of colonialism and evangelization of the whole of African continent. These historical and sociological experiences change our modes of thoughts from rustic state to the perceived reformed state without any critical interpretive models of reality thereby establishing knowledge-based encapsulation of Africans to the point of subservience and abject submissiveness. Consequently, these socio-historical arrangements have created the false image of Africa as a continent that perpetually depends on Europe for civilization and sustainable economic recovery [Said, 1994, p 56 Bhabha, 1994, p 123, Boehmer, 2005, p 34].

Ambivalently, colonialism in Nigeria redefined African cultural worldview and social relations in consistence with the platforms offered by western education thereby classifying African people into the bipolar structures of the educated and the uneducated, the literates and the illiterates as well as the learned and the unlearned. The members of the camps in the bipolar structures have access to different opportunities and privileges with the eventual consequences on the creation of class-based society which negates the cultural nationalism and collective national identities that predated colonialism. Following the newly constructed colonial societies where Africans could no longer share homogeneous African ideology of communalism and collectivism, there are differences along the line of educational level, privileges in colonial services as teachers, lay readers, domestic staff and catechists. The pains were heavy on the minds of the underprivileged who can also be described as the subaltern (the colonial population which suffers exclusion from the colonial power matrix while its antithetical meaning is hegemony) [Gramsci, 1971. p. 55 Guha, 1982, Spivak, 1980. p 90]. In its general sense, the subaltern refers to the class of people who are oppressed and placed socially, politically and geographically outside of the hegemonic power structure of the colony and which Gramsci’s cultural hegemony are denied a voice within the power structures of society [Akoh, 2023, s 10-11]. Even if the subaltern cannot speak in unity to form a state with a view to changing their situation [Gramsci, 1971, s 11], they can at least protest their subalternity in writing [Akoh, 2023. s.45] as found in the thematic foci of plays/dramatic texts of the first generation of Nigerian playwrights such as Wole Soyinka, Ola Rotimi, James Ene Henshaw and John Pepper Clark.

In the category of the first generation of Nigerian playwrights, the present writers focus on Wole Soyinka owing to the fact of his reputation as the first African Nobel Laureate and the topicality of the themes of his plays on hegemonic shift – a temporary displacement of the dominant paradigm before a resurfacing of another hegemony. Two of the prominent plays of Wole Soyinka that treats European cultural hegemony against the backdrop of the subaltern African culture

are *The Lion and the Jewel* [Jewel, 1962. p.67] and *Death and the King's Horseman* [Horseman, 1975, p 60]. Particularly, the focus of the present study is on *The Lion and the Jewel* based on the fact that it has a pan-African representation with dual linguistic expressions in English and French languages – the two dominant languages of colonial administration in Africa. Besides, the play's subtle criticism of inverted reality and the construction of cultural identities as reflected in the characterization and plot calls for critical attention. With the conceptualization of inverted reality, the present writers chart a new course in the analysis of the characters and roles of principal characters – Baroka, Lakunle, Sidi and Sadiku – with a view to establishing how few of them, if not all, have been the opposite of what they claim to be representing between tradition and modernity. Doing this, the article unmasks inverted reality through the language and action of the characters individually or collectively without compromising the spectra of interpretive meanings overtly or covertly represented in the play. Also, the present writers do not excuse the subjective actualization of inverted reality and cultural response to modernity in the play.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

At its first premiere in 1959 and the first publication in 1962, the simplest interpretations given to Wole Soyinka's *The Lion and the Jewel* are the class between European and African cultures; the ideological clash between tradition and modernity as well as between the old and the new generations. These interpretations resonate in Showmya and Sinega's [Sinega, 2021, p 23] *Cultural Representation in Wole Soyinka's The Lion and the Jewel*, Watt's [Jewel, 2008, p.79] *Tradition v Modernity: Wole Soyinka's The Lion and the Jewel*, Reddy's [Jewel Reddy, 2013] *Cultural Conflict in Wole Soyinka's Play The Lion and the Jewel* as well as Lalmawizuala's [Jewel, 2016, p.88] *Tradition versus Colonial Mentality: Understanding the Effects of Colonization in The Lion and the Jewel*. This does not overlook studies on the play from the perspectives of gender, discourse analysis as well as postcolonial and anthropological studies. Thus, the play has undergone different ideological configurations as a response to the indented meanings inscribed in the text through its characterization and overall subject matter.

A simple summary of the play shows a battle for love between a young teacher, Lakunle and an old village head, Baroka. With series of events running into one another, thereby establishing the ideological warfare between tradition and modernity, the play comes to a conclusive end with a marriage between Sidi (the village damsel) and Baroka (Baale of Ilujinle). Beyond this simple plot of the play is the ideological seal of identity construction and inverted reality premised on knowing and becoming of the principal characters most especially Lakunle, Baroka, Sidi and Sadiku. In view of this, the present writers uphold the assertion that “ideology signifies ideas and beliefs which help to legitimate the interests of a ruling group or class specifically by means of distortion and dissimulation” [Eagleton, 1991, p 34]. The strategies of distortion adopted in the representation of

ideology subject it to endless interpretations in life and literature. This is the case in the interpretive adventures into the representation of identity construction and inverted reality in the whole gamut of the play that interrogates the commonality of educated and uneducated Africans as [re-] presented in the characterization of Lakunle (an educated Europeanized African) and Baroka (a pure aboriginal African). Despite the difference in their sociological experience and educational standard, the fact still remains that both of them are Africans.

Considering the sociological background of the play, one may state that Soyinka's experience in London as a student provided a prompt for the subject matter of the play which presents a psycho-social conflicts between rusticity of African culture and the presumed modernity of European culture. This situation has been a motif in other literary genre of Soyinka most especially one of his most celebrated poem, Telephone Conversation. While in London, perhaps, Soyinka had witnessed evils of racial discrimination and cultural chauvinism of the whites thereby reliving in him the essence of African cultural renaissance. Also, Soyinka who has been properly rooted in African [Yoruba] culture feels the urge to question the fake cultural identity of most Africans who have been carried away by the European mentality of cultural supremacy over African culture. These Europeanized Africans usually suffer from inverted reality such like Lakunle in *The Lion and the Jewel*.

There is a sharp contrast between pure naivety of Sidi and the pretended modernity of Lakunle especially in the representation of their African identity. Lakunle copiously demonstrates unrepentant arrogance and inverted reality which is antithetical to the African communal ethos. No matter the extent of his learning, he forgets the fact that he still remains an African and his behaviour must be consistent with African normative standard of behaviour. Contrarily, he sees African culture unmatched with his newly acquired European culture through education in order to achieve his selfish end. In an impressionistic manner of convincing Sidi to marry him without paying a bride price (a customary practice among Yoruba people to consolidate a marriage), Lakunle uses a collection of negative adjectives to describe African [Yoruba] culture – his culture of birth and identity. While describing Yoruba culture, Lakunle describes it as “a savage custom, barbaric, out dated, rejected, denounced, accursed, excommunicated, archaic, degrading, humiliating, unspeakable, redundant, retrogressive, remarkable, unpalatable” [Soyinka, 1962, p 123]. The arrogant attitude of Lakunle towards everything African replicates the attitude of few educated Africans that Ngugi wa Thiong'o describes in his *Decolonizing the mind*. This category of Africans consciously distance themselves from their cultural beliefs and practices following the “cultural bomb” unleashed by the colonial hegemony of Europeans. In his submission, Wa Thiong'o averred thus:

... the biggest weapon ... unleashed by imperialism against that collective defiance is the cultural bomb. The effect of a cultural bomb is to annihilate a people's belief in their names, in their languages, in their environment,

in their heritage of struggle, in their unity, in their capacities and ultimately in themselves. It makes them see their past as one wasteland of non-achievement and it makes them want to distance themselves from that wasteland. [Ngugi, 2007, p 233]

Lakunle has been hit by the cultural bomb as he does not see any value in the African culture. One can, however, question the honesty in Lakunle's attitude which is precipitated by his unwillingness to pay Sidi's bride price. Based on this, there is inversion of his reality in line with the duality of his cultural representation. No doubt, Lakunle is an African with 'half education' which qualifies him to be a primary school teacher in a village school. With the position, Lakunle sees himself above everyone in the village and thereby expects everyone to see him as an opinion leader on social, political and cultural matters. Lakunle is, however, displeased with the fact that people of Ilujinle do not see any sense in his actions and utterances. In a face-saving manner, Lakunle retorts as follows.

... what is a jewel to pigs?

If now I am misunderstood by you

And your race of savages, I rise above taunts

And remain unruffled. [Ngugi, 2007, p. 5.]

The rhetorical question used by Lakunle is a subtle reflection of his inverted reality which ridicules his situation of half-education and cultural bigotry. He is dissociating himself from the culture that nurtures and prepares him for the little European education he has acquired. With this attitude, he visibly demonstrated what Lois Tyson described as unhomeliness which does not mean lack of home. In his clarification of unhomeliness, Tyson avers that

Being "unhomed" is not the same as being homeless. To be unhomed is to feel not at home even in your own home because you are not at home in yourself: your cultural identity crisis has made you a psychological refugee, so to speak. [Tyson, 2006, p. 419]

The unhomeliness of Lakunle is seen in his psychological dissociation with anything African following his deluded vision of refined European culture. Erroneously and as an indication of his inverted reality, Lakunle does not see himself as part of Ilujinle despite that his ancestry is from the place. His education has given him a bloated conception of African identity as nothing to be reckoned with. His action and misconceived notion of African identity is like a proverbial kettle calling pot black. In actual reality, characters like Sidi, Sadiku and Baroka are better than Lakunle because they psychologically and sociologically connect with their nativity of African culture although with some traces of cultural infusion from the colonial mentality of Lakunle. For instance, Sidi appreciates the sanity and wisdom of African culture and hence her insistence for the payment of the bride price before marrying Lakunle. This insistence is shown in the following excerpt.

SIDI: Now there you go again. One little thing and you must chirrup like a cockatoo. You talk and talk and deafen me with words which always sound the same and make no meaning. I have told you, and I say it again. I shall marry you today, next week or any day you name. But my bride-price must first be paid. [Tyson, 2006, p. 60]

The excerpt reveals the firmness of Sidi in the cultural ideology of virginity and bride-price. In African [Yoruba] cultural episteme, a maiden such like Sidi is expected to preserve her virginity and thus the need for a very handsome bride-price to reward the bride's family for proper moral upbringing of their daughter. It is, therefore, a general belief that a maiden whose bride price is not paid is no more a virgin. The deduction from this situation is that Sidi demonstrates the actual reality of her cultural background. Similarly, Sidi has accepted patriarchal configuration of her sex as lacking in self-determination. Just like Sidi, Sadiku also demonstrates constriction to the patriarchal definition of her sex. She gladly accepts her roles as a wife in the polygamous harem of Baroka – first as an inheritance and later as the most senior wife on list of wives to Baroka, the Baale of Ilujinle. Considering the aura that surrounds her position as the most senior wife in the compound of Baroka, Sadiku lives in Eldorado with respect and honor attached to her social reputation as a “queen”. While convincing Sid to be a wife (the youngest and the most favorite of Baroka), Sadiku emphasizes the ‘comfort’ which she (Sadiku) enjoys and which awaits Sidi. The following excerpt reveals thus:

SADIKU: Sidi, have you considered what a life of bliss awaits you? Baroka swears to take no other wife after you. Do you know what it is to be the Bale's latest wife? I'll tell you. When he dies – and that should not be long; even the Lion has to die sometime – well, when he does, it means that you will have the honour of being the senior wife of the new Bale. And just think, until Baroka dies, you shall be his favourite. No living in the outhouse for you, my girl. Your place will always be in the palace; first as the latest bride, and afterwards, as the head of the new harem ... It is, a rich life, Sidi. I know. I have been in that position for forty-one years. [Tyson, 2006, pp. 20-21]

The deduction from Sadiku's assertion is that the womenfolk in the play have conveniently subscribed to the pigeonholed representation of feminine gender. Following the patriarchal representation of feminine gender in Yoruba society and the play, Sadiku does not see anything wrong in her responsibilities of satisfying the masculine ego of Baroka and other male folks such as Lakunle. Considering the gender representation of women in patriarchal society and in

Soyinka's *The Lion and the Jewel*, Haste describes women as "need-meeter to others" [Haste, 1993, p. 69].

With the above trajectory of plot development in the play and the consistent ideological conflicts between Lakunle and Baroka, the latter is placed at the center of attraction thereby suffering from inverted reality. Baroka faces the dilemma of "in-betweenness" with close reference to the sustainable hold on tradition or absolute rejection of modernity. This specificity in the critique of the characterization of Baroka forms the bulk of discussion in the later part of this article. Baroka sees Lakunle as an albatross that should be carried carefully across his neck and this informs why he adopts diplomacy anytime both of them are in contacts. Initially, they are both contenders on a fundamental issue of modernity and civilization of the whole of Ilujinle. Another issue of battle for love creeps in after the publication of the magazine which announces to the whole world that Sidi is the village belle. It is at this moment that Baroka sees the need to take a new wife and the target is Sidi, the latest beauty-champion of Ilujinle. On hearing the declaration of Sidi as the village belle, Baroka reorts that "yes, yes ... it is five full months since last I took a wife ... five full months." [Haste, 1993, p. 18] Following this retort, Baroka confidently informs Ailatu (one his wives and the latest before the marriage with Sidi) that:

BAROKA: You have no time, my dear. Tonight I hope to take another wife. And the honour of this task, you know, belongs by right to my latest choice. [Haste, 1993, p. 18]

Baroka hopes to achieve his goal at all cost. This informs his action of lying to Sadiku that he has become impotent. This action is based on the prediction of the actual reality of Sadiku and Sidi that they irrational in information management. The trick works and Sidi becomes victims of Baroka's ploy - she ends up on his bed without the payment of bride price.

From the previous discussion in this article, Baroka and Lakunle are presented as characters with inverted realities owing to their mixed feelings towards tradition and modernity. These two characters demonstrate, what Du Bois has described as double consciousness, the situation of psychological tension between the margin and the center. Du Bois' description of double consciousness as given below is central to the discourse on the inverted reality demonstrated by Lakunle and Baroka. In his description, Dubois avers that double consciousness is

... a peculiar sensation, this double consciousness, this sense of always looking at one's self through the eyes of others, of measuring one's soul by the tape of a world that looks on in amused contempt and pity. One ever feels his two-ness, an American, a Negro; two souls two thoughts two unreconciled strivings; two warring ideals in one dark body, whose dogged strength alone keeps it from being torn asunder. [Du Bois, 1997, p. 38]

Although Du Bois used the term to describe Negro's cultural attitude in America, the signification of double consciousness is also relevant to describe the

disposition of Africans to their native culture after their exposure to European education, culture and religion as we have in the actions of the likes of Baroka and Lakunle. These two characters suffered from Oedipus complex (superiority-inferiority complex) between the nativity of their tradition and their respective inducted modernity through education and civilization. The Oedipus complex between the duo of Baroka and Lakunle becomes complicated, perhaps, because of their different processes of induction to modernity – Lakunle through education and Baroka through civilization. Consequently, they both hold each other with suspicions before the surfacing of Sidi as the bait to further fuel the ideological warfare between the Lion of Ilujinle and the school master of Ilujinle. Ironically, each of them claim unflinching knowledge and understanding of the culture they uphold but with no proper wisdom to see the meeting point between tradition and modernity. It is their lack of wisdom that represents them as characters with inverted reality with dogmatism and fanatical execution of their cultural beliefs. Both of them have been diluted with the lost native intelligence that can prompt them towards purgation. This situation will be effectively enunciated in the later part of this article. The defiance of Lakunle to tradition and the resistance of Baroka to modernity are counterproductive to the postcolonial transformation of the country no matter the latent intentions they may have for this. They, therefore, revealingly demonstrate the malaise of inverted reality in their thoughts and actions.

Can Modernity Live without Tradition?

In *Tradition vs. Modernity: The Continuing Dichotomy of Values in European Society* [Galland & Lemel, 2008, p 67], Galland and Lemel argues that tradition and modernity are the same side of the coin with one complement the other. This reveals that one is not superior to another. The only problem seen in the collaborative relationship between tradition and modernity is the subjective interpretation of reality with the process of acculturation and socialization. This is the exact case with Lakunle whose half-education has infected him with cultural bigotry and short-sightedness to understand his own folly of moving against the culture that nurtured him. With his half-education, he has pronounced himself to the whole of Ilujinle as the epitome of civilization and modernity. One, then, wonders the kind of education that he passes on to the students under his pastoral care and literacy without affecting the sustainability of tradition.

Baroka, on the other hand, shows the manifestation of traditional African men who were not comfortable with modernity and civilization at the initial stage. Baroka's fear, perhaps, is that he will lose all the privileges attached to his office as the Bale of Ilujinle. In his deluded vision, he is making efforts to frustrate the construction of railway that will connect Ilujinle with other big cities and towns most especially Lagos by offering bribes to the people working on the project. What Baroka has failed to realize, perhaps, because of his lack of western education, is that the infrastructural development in Ilujinle will bring more opportunities and privileges thereby legitimizing his concrete hold on the whole

village. On this idea, Blom [Blom, 2002, p 199] and Senyojo [Senyojo, 2004, p 123] have argued that one of best ways for the traditional communities to advance and achieve more in the contemporary social matrix is the dynamic absorption of the ideals of modernity in parts or holistically.

Despite the fact that Lakunle and Baroka have points of intersection culturally especially during a performance, they are not serious minded in the harmonization of tradition and modernity. The duo usually operate at two parallel directions. As soon as Baroka enters the venue of the performance, Lakunle makes efforts to escape from the scene. This is revealed in the following excerpt.

BAROKA: Akowe. Teacher wa, mista Lakunle.

LAKUNLE: A good morning to you sir.

BAROKA: Guru morin, guru morn, nbh! That is all we hear from alakowe'. You call at his house hoping he sends for beer but all you get is guru morin. Will guru morin wet my throat? Well well our man of knowledge, I hope you have no query for an old man today.

LAKUNLE: No complaints.

BAROKA: And we are feuding in something I have forgotten.

LAKUNLE: Feuding sir? I see no cause at all.

BAROKA: Well the play was much alive until I came; now everything stops and you were leaving us. After all I know the story and I came in right on cue. It makes me feel as if I was Chief Baseje.

LAKUNLE: One hardly thinks the Bale will have the times for such childish nonsense.

BAROKA: A-ah mister Lakunle. Without these things you call nonsense, a Bale's life will be pretty dull. Well now that you say I am welcome, shall we resume your play.... [Senyojo, 2004, p. 13-14]

The familiar play that Baroka makes reference to in the dialogue is that of the lost traveler. This is an indication that Ilujinle has had previous opportunities to advance technologically and economically but the negligence of the people and the pre-planned frustration of the efforts by Baroka thwart Ilujinle's graduation to modernity. In fact, Baroka is the presumed name, Baseje (a spoiler of good things) that he calls himself. He has been using his authority to disturb the smooth transition of Ilujinle to modernity. The lost traveler that forms the subject matter of the performance that generated confrontation between Baroka and Lakunle could not achieve anything in Ilujinle and hence he left in dejection and frustration. Baroka is self-seeking and pleasure-seeking, as shown in the dialogue with Lakunle. He (Baroka) wants everything that will satisfy his id even at the detriment of the entire village. The only indigenous achievement of Baoka is the central toilet of the village. Although Soyinka does not mention how the school came into

Ilujinle, our speculation, however, is that it has the involvement of the government that have seen the need to develop Ilujinle. The negative attitude of Baroka to modernity and infrastructural development in Ilujinle aligns with the view of Petkovic that “like the form of regression and stagnancy in culture, traditionalism opposes each change or innovation, it withstands to modernization, stigmatizing everything that carries with it the accompanying sound of new, other, and different” [Petkovic, 2007, p 55].

Instead of concentrating on the serious business of modern development in Ilujinle, Baroka creates time for frivolous life style. What he fails to realize is that it might be slow, modernity will still live with or without collaboration. This argument is premised on the position of Gyegyey [Gyekye, 1997, p 34] that tradition are synthesis and not an antithesis to each other. Thus, there is a need for a synthetic relationship between Baroka and Lakunle – the innovation in education in conjunction with proactive traditional institutions have the potential to usher in a new age, an advancement in technology and a new epoch in the socio-economic history of Ilujinle.

The synthetic relationship between tradition and modernity as proposed by Gyegyey is not strange to Ilujinle, a village that has been points of attraction somehow to outside world of Lagos. This shows that Ilujinle is already on the path of modernity and development despite the machinations of Baroka who fails to understand that modernity can only prompt advancement of the existing tradition. The story of socio-human relations in Ilujinle changes with the arrival of magazine which arrives from Lagos. The magazine, in the context of the play and based on the interpretive approach adopted by the present article, symbolizes modernity because it opens up Ilujinle for further modern development. Similarly, the arrival of the magazine in Ilujinle complicates the conflict and advances the plot of the play. This is because the prominence and recognition given to Sidi’s photograph on the cover of the magazine awakes the lustful feeling of Baroka towards her. The following excerpt reveals as follow:

THIRD GIRL:

Yes, yes, he did. But the Bale is still feasting his eyes on the images. Oh, Sidi, he was right. You are beautiful. On the cover of the book is an image of you from here [touches the top of her head] to here [her stomach]. And in the middle leaves, from the beginning of one leaf right across to the end of another, is one of you from head to toe. Do you remember it? It was the one for which he made you stretch your arms towards the sun. [Rapturously.] Oh, Sidi, you looked as if, at that moment, the sun himself had been your lover. [They all gasp with pretended shock at this blasphemy and one slaps her playfully on the buttocks.]

FIRST GIRL: The Bale is jealous, but he pretends to be proud of you. And when this man tells him how famous you are in the capital, he pretends to be pleased, saying how much honour and fame you have brought to the village.

SIDI: [with amazement.] Is not Baroka's image in the book at all?

SECOND GIRL: [contemptuous.] Oh yes, it is. But it would have been much better for the Bale if the stranger had omitted him altogether. His image is in a little corner somewhere in the book, and even that corner he shares with one of the village latrines. [Gyekye, 1997, p. 11]

With her photograph prominently displayed at the outer cover page of the magazine, Sidi's beauty has been pronounced to the world. Consequently, Baroka sees this as an opportunity to add to his fame without courting modernity. This is an erroneous assumption because with the magazine and marriage to Sidi, he cannot escape the inroads of modernity into Ilujinle because "the world around us is growing more complex by the day; reality is changing or mutating at an amazing speed" [Layiwola, 2010, p. 17]. The world around Ilujinle is becoming dynamic and changing as hinted by Lakunle with his constant references to the civilization in Ibadan and Lagos while making efforts to convince Sidi. The arrival of the magazine only validates the claims of civilization made by Lakunle.

At a deeper level of analysis of Baroka's ideology or attitude to modernity, one can say that he is not totally averse to the evolving change in Ilujinle. His problem, perhaps, is the fear that the emerging modernity will alter the normative values of his people. With this, one can say that Baroka conceives modernity in line with the philosophical thoughts of Auguste Comte, Karl Marx, Emile Durkheim and Max Weber who have argued that a paradigm shift often accompanies modernity. This is not to say that Baroka does not want modernity. The basic issue that he has is the approach and the fear of the unknown. For this reason, he wants the whole process to be gradual, systemic and organic. It can, therefore, be said that his conception of modernity aligns with Emile Durkheim's ideal of transcended solidarity from the mechanical phase to the social phase of solidarity. In *The Lion and the Jewel*, the village maidens unanimously appreciate the magazine with no exemption of Baroka and Lakunle but with different vested interests. This reveals that they are all prepared for the imminent change that will be ushered in by modernity. In a review of the social solidarity proposed by Emile Durkheim, Malik and Malik [Malik and Malik, 2022, p 11] identify four operational levels of social solidarity – (i) the system of bond between individuals and society (ii) the bonds between individuals within a society (iii) members of society are united by ties to that society (iv) solidarity refers to the intensity of the

cohesion of attachments which link the individuals to their society [Malik & Malik, 2022, p. 7–10]. We can, therefore, see the traces of social solidarity in Ilujinle thereby preparing the village for modernity.

Baroka's leaning towards the path of modernity is revealed through his series of dialogues with Sidi while making efforts to woo her. He makes Sidi understand that he believes in modernity but not in the approach adopted by Lakunle. During the re-enactment of the stranger with devil horse, Baroka acknowledges the sense in Lakunle's prompt towards modernity. This is shown in the following excerpt.

BAROKA: And where would the village be, robbed of such wisdom as Mister Lakunle dispenses daily? Who would tell us where we go wrong? Eh, Mister Lakunle? [Malik & Malik, 2022, p. 17]

With this acknowledgement, there is a path to modernity. From another perspective, one can say that Baroka publicly states this to endear Sidi to himself based on the open knowledge of the likeness that Sidi and Baroka have for each other. This argument still takes to the view that Sidi is the bait or rather, she is the signification of the center of gravity for the cultural tension between tradition and modernity. Similarly, Baroka flatters Sidi with the "superior knowledge" of Lakunle with a view to swaying Sidi's love towards himself. The following excerpt reveals thus:

BAROKA: Ah, I forget. This is the price I pay. Once every week, for being progressive. Prompted by the school teacher, my servants were prevailed upon to form something they call The Palace Workers' Union. And in keeping with the habits -- I am told -- of modern towns. This is their day off. [Malik & Malik, 2022, p. 37]

Although the above dialogue is a flattery of Lakunle's conception of modernity, Baroka is surreptitiously adopting it. Apart from genuinely acknowledging the knowledge of Lakunle, Baroka has also taken some steps towards modernity with the construction of the stamp-making machine kept in the secrecy of his palace. While showcasing the machine for Sidi, he stated that:

BAROKA: The work dear child, of the palace blacksmiths. Built in full secrecy. All is not well with it -- But I will find the cause and then Ilujinle will boast its own tax on paper, made with stamps like this. For long I dreamt it. And here it stands, child of my thoughts. [Malik & Malik, 2022, p. 49]

The deduction from Baroka's assertion is that, perhaps, he prefers endogenous modernity – a form of modernity which grows from within the village. This simply means that he does not want imposed modernity that people will find it difficult to manage or relate as in the case of Lakunle. The endogenous modernity will aid in the technological development of the land and the scientific thinking of the people within the trajectory home-grown development. With the

preference for the endogenous modernity, Baroka want to make a point that Africa has native intelligence and cognitive perspicuity which can propel the continent towards technological advancement and sustainable scientific discoveries. The advancement in technology will serve as the catalysts for urbanization and industrial revolution in consistence with the averment of Schaniel that “the new technology may create change in society, and that the direction of change is determined by the nature and function (use) of that technology in the adopting culture” [Schaniel, 1988. p. 491–502]. Baroka may therefore be aware of the capabilities of technology to evolve a new society of surprises and pains and for this reason, he aspires modernity that is self-generative, dynamic and flexible to the sociological, economic and cultural needs of the people. Another important point registered Baroka’s action is that Africa is not a void geographical space with no home-grown knowledge system that can propel science and technology. This situation, therefore, explains the joy and satisfaction of Baroka at the unveiling of the machine before Sidi.

Since “a text is characterised by its constituent form of language (langue + parole), grammar, syntax and lexicology/phono/semantics graphetics, graphology, tenor, tone, structure, and cultural artefacts that define its ideological contents” [Fashina, 2023, p. 19], a critic of a text needs to enervate all the nuances of meanings overtly or covertly expressed in the text. Following this submission, a text yields to different connotative and denotative interpretations thereby becoming a writerly text [Barthes, 1970, p 11] (a text which generates multiple meanings based episodes of readings and literary criticisms). It is on this understanding that the present article critiques *The Lion and the Jewel* beyond the general conception of cultural conflicts between tradition and modernity or ideological conflicts between the old and the new generations. Rather, the present article reformulates the textual ideology of the play within the framework of cultural synthesis between tradition and modernity.

With the characterization and the approach of conflict resolution in the play, Soyinka does not overtly present theme of cultural or ideological conflicts. The inference from the play, rather, underlines the ideals of cultural synthesis as received from the dialogues of Baroka and Sidi whose dispositions towards modernity were not outright rejection of the evolving change in Ilujinle. Their responses towards modernity is conscious appraisal of the strength and weakness of the “new order” that is being preached to them by one of them, Lakunle. It is also the submission of this article that the negative attitude of Sidi and Baroka towards modernity is informed by the radicalist and escapist approach that Lakunle adopts in the preaching of modernity to the people of Ilujinle. Instead of taking him serious, the people of Ilujinle see him as self-serving in an attempt to marry the village belle without paying the customary bride price. All these have not indicated a serious cultural or ideological conflicts but a misrepresentation of purpose towards achieve a common goal – the evolvement of a modern culture in Ilujinle.

The marriage of Sidi to Baroka at the end of the play does not really mean the loss of modernity to the said cultural/ideological battle as some critics such as Watt (2008) have made us believe. It is, rather, an attempt by Wole Soyinka to emphasize cultural synthesis and the re-invigoration of tradition and modernity for a sustainable symbiotic relationship. The marriage between Baroka and Sidi, therefore, is a synthesis of the positive energies of the old generation and the new generation to procreate modernity. Thus, the marriage is not an economic loss to the growth and development of Ilujinle. In fact, Sidi becomes convinced about the competence and native intelligence of Baroka to transform Ilujinle upon a closer discussion between them. Surprisingly, Sidi avers that “I can no longer see the meaning, Baroka. Now that you speak almost like the school teacher, except your words fly on a different path, I find . . .” [Barthes, 1970, p. 52] This new discovery of the competence of Baroka may even induce the sexual relationship between them – an action which culminated in marriage at the end of the play. The issue of cultural synthesis is also echoed in the return of the magazine (the totem of modernity) to Lakunle. By not tearing the magazine, Sidi still sees the value in the document. The primary problem, however, is the source of the magazine.

Critically, Baroka is aware of the need for the cultural synthesis and synergy between the old and the new generation to ensure sustainable modernity. This is based on the understanding that modernity only thrives on the existing tradition starting from the process of conception to the stage of deployment. Any attempt to overlook this stringent process towards modernity will amount to “mocking the real wounds of the inflictions where they are deepest and most enduring” [Osundare, 1993, p. 7]. This is the exact situation that Baroka wants to avoid by insisting on cultural synthesis and home-grown modernity hinge on collaboration and cooperation among the stakeholders irrespective of the generation, age and levels of education. An instance of this argument is seen in the dialogue between Baroka and Sidi.

BAROKA: The old must flow into the new, Sidi, Not blind itself for stand foolishly Apart. A girl like you must inherit Miracles which age alone reveals. Is this not so?

SIDI: Everything you say, Bale, Seems wise to me.

BAROKA: Yesterday's wine alone is strong and blooded, child, and though the Christians' holy book denies the truth of this, old wine thrives best Within a new bottle. The coarseness is mellowed down, and the rugged wine Acquires a full and rounded body . . . Is this not so -- my child? [Quite overcome, Sidi nods.]

BAROKA: Those who know little of Baroka think His life one pleasure-living course. But the monkey sweats, my child, the monkey sweats, it is only the hair upon his back which still deceives the world . . . [Osundare, 1993, p. 53]

This unearthing of another possible interpretation of the play demonstrates a liberal approach to cultural nationalism and modernity. Baroka is not self-conceited as Lakunle has presented him in the play. Rather, he demonstrates rationalism in the adoption of modernist model for his village. In consistence with the discussion in this article, there is no statement on cultural victory. In fact, there is no victory and no vanquished. Rather, there is a need for endogenous approach to the evolvment and deployment of sustainable modernity.

CONCLUSION

This article discusses representation of inverted reality and cultural response to modernity in Soyinka's *The Lion and the Jewel*. The review of previous works on the play reveals a general conceptualization of cultural/ideological conflicts as the basic thematic construct of the play. Although this general position on the play is valid, the present writers engaged in the reformulation of ideas with the argument that the focus of the play is quest for cultural synthesis between tradition and modernity. This idea is articulated with due consideration for the characterization of Lakunle, Baroka, Sidi and Sadiku. In the course of our discussion, it was argued that Lakunle and Baroka suffered from inverted reality because their lives and actions are antithetical to what they stand for in the play. It was also argued that the position of the play, as interpreted by the present writers, is that Baroka opts for endogenous model of modernity which is expected to be participatory, dynamic and flexible to the needs of the people.

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